
Emulando amplificadores y pedales de guitarra eléctrica con inteligencia artificial

10 de abril de 2025

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*Basado en el TFG del curso 2023-2024
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Contenidos

**ESTADO
DEL ARTE**

ARQUITECTURA
WAVENET

RESULTADOS
OBTENIDOS

CONCLUSIONES

1950's Tweed Deluxe

FENDER "DELUXE" LAYOUT MODEL 5E3

Annotated by Rob Robinette

F - EE

NOTICE

VOLTAGES READ TO GROUND
WITH ELECTRONIC VOLTMETER
VALUES SHOWN \pm OR - 20 %

Estado del arte

Plugins

Soldano SLO-100 X

The legendary amplifier that originated American high-gain tone.

€119.00

[Learn more](#)

[Free trial](#)

Fortin Nameless Suite X

Precisely engineered brutality. A legendary amplifier replicated in a beautiful plugin.

€119.00

[Learn more](#)

[Free trial](#)

Emuladores de equipamiento: *profilers*

BIAS FX 2

Bank 1 *Little Wing Marshall Univibe

120.0 TAP

STORE

Routing Single Dual

Scene Add Clear Undo

Emuladores más tradicionales

Voltage Sag

ORIGINAL

INPUT VOLUME

GUITAR MATCH

QUICK SNAP

OUTPUT SETTING

OUTPUT VOLUME

INPUT VOLUME control with a slider from -60 to 6 and a barcode-like display.

AUTO LOCK control with a lock icon.

GUITAR MATCH control with a guitar icon and ON/OFF toggle.

QUICK SNAP control with a 2x4 grid of buttons numbered 1 through 8.

OUTPUT SETTING control with a speaker icon and ON/OFF toggle.

OUTPUT VOLUME control with a slider from -60 to 6 and a MUTE button.

Article

Real-Time Guitar Amplifier Emulation with Deep Learning [†]

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† This paper is an extended version of our paper published in the Proceedings of the 16th International Sound and Music Computing Conference SMC-19 in Malaga, Spain, 28–31 May 2019.

Received: 12 December 2019; Accepted: 15 January 2020; Published: 21 January 2020

Véase [1].

GuitarML

Véase [2].

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Arquitectura WaveNet

Ilustración extraída de [3].

DeepMind

Text-to-speech

$\hat{\mathbf{x}}$: Variable aleatoria que modeliza una onda digital

$$\mathbf{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_{N-1}, x_N)$$

$$p(\mathbf{x}) = \prod_{k=1}^N p(x_k | x_1, \dots, x_{k-1})$$

$$N = K(M - 1) + 1$$

*Causal
convolutional stacks*

$K = 3$
 $M = 2$
 $N = 4$

*Dilated causal
convolutional stacks*

$K = 3$
 $M = 2$
 $N = 8$

*Dilated causal
convolutional stacks*

$K = 3$
 $M = 3$
 $N = 15$

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Resultados

Modelando pedales reales

Con la colaboración de
Diego M. Continente

Comparación de señales (ESR = 0.0153)

Error absoluto (zoom)

Espectrograma del error

Comparación de espectros de magnitud

Contenidos

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Referencias

- [1] A. Wright, D. Eero-Pekka y V. V. Juvela Lauri, «Real-Time Guitar Amplifier Emulation with DeepLearning,» *Applied Sciences*, 2020.
 - [2] K. Bloemer. «GuitarML: Machine Learning For Rock & Roll.» (2024), dirección: <https://guitarml.com/>.
 - [3] A. Van den Oord, S. Dieleman, H. Zen et al., «WaveNet: A Generative Model for Raw Audio,» 2016. *arXiv*: 1609.03499.
-

A yellow emoji with a hand on its chin, looking thoughtful. The emoji has large, dark eyes and a slightly open mouth. The text is overlaid on the emoji's face.

¡Gracias por vuestra
atención!

Apéndice

La arquitectura WaveNet en detalle

Arquitectura general

- Bloque oculto
- Bloque residual

Arquitectura general

- Bloque oculto
- Bloque residual
- Skip-connections
- Mixer lineal

Model	WaveNet1	WaveNet2	WaveNet3
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Activation	Gated	Gated	Gated
Layers	10	18	18
Channels	16	8	16

Tabla e ilustraciones extraídas de [1].

Apéndice

Sobre la implementación

Tecnologías Python

Tecnologías

C++

Trabajando con una Raspberry Pi 5

- ¿Throttling?
- ¿Problemas de compatibilidad?
- ¿Sistema operativo?
- ¿Cómo recibir el audio?
- ¿Será lo suficientemente potente?
- (...)

ELK Audio OS

Audio/MIDI Settings

Feedback Loop: Mute audio input

Output: snd_rpi_hifiberry_dacplusadcpro, HiFiBerry... Test

Input: snd_rpi_hifiberry_dacplusadcpro, HiFiBerry...

Active output channels:

- channel 1 + 2
- channel 3 + 4
- channel 5 + 6
- channel 7 + 8

Active input channels:

- channel 1 + 2
- channel 3 + 4
- channel 5 + 6
- channel 7 + 8

Sample rate: 44100 Hz

Audio buffer size: 512 samples (11.6 ms)

Active MIDI inputs: Midi Through Port-0

Raspberry Pi OS

¿DAW?
¿Plugins?
